

APPROACHES TO ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN KINDERGARTEN

Abdurakhmonova Umida Vafo qizi

Gulistan State University Faculty of Psychology and Social Sciences 3rd year student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10992617>

Based on the approach to understanding the essence of environmental problems, a different understanding of the essence of environmental education is characterized and it is proved that only an approach aimed at discovering unity with nature by a child, discovering nature in himself and feeling himself a part of nature can be effective today. The article describes some specific requirements for a teacher who is able to conduct environmental education within the framework of the selected approach. The author describes the experience of work on environmental education of the DOD. Folk pedagogy is actively used in the kindergarten's work system, ecological performances are staged, a research system, ecological routes, actions have been developed, a nature room, a phytocafe, a svetelka, a mini zoo, various natural areas on the territory of the preschool, a TV project "Fontanelle", clubs for parents and much more have been created. The author sees the result of the work in the moral education of graduates, which is noted by school teachers, in the support of the work carried out by the teaching staff of the preschool by parents who act as our allies in the environmental education of children.

The violation of the ecological balance on our planet is one of the most significant problems of our time. The realization of the root cause of such a state of the environment led to the conclusion that the culture that gave rise to the technocratic civilization came into conflict with the laws of nature - by consuming, society exceeded the biosphere's ability to make up for what was lost. Therefore, the solution to environmental problems should be sought primarily in the field of people's environmental management culture, in the development of such forms of communication with the environment that would be adequate to people's desire to change the situation for the better.

In this regard, environmental education is a significant and widespread area of work of educational organizations. Environmental education has been actively conducted for more than a quarter of a century. However, it is still difficult to talk about improving the environmental culture of our citizens. Why? It seems to us that one of the reasons is the difference in approaches to understanding the very essence of environmental issues and the corresponding essence of environmental education. There are statements in science that alleviate the severity of environmental problems: "Environmental issues are solved by themselves in the course of evolutionary development"; "Man is a biological being who naturally took the top step in the hierarchy of organisms. You need to rely on the natural order of things. Man has survival resources that are not yet clear"; "Only man realizes the value of nature, and it is up to him to decide how to use it." Ideas of this type also regulate the behavior of some people at the level of everyday consciousness. We have identified three approaches to understanding the essence of environmental problems, which (each in its own way) prove the need to foster environmental culture:

1. The Creator created a well-thought-out and beautiful world. Nature is a temple, only then a workshop.
2. The conditions of human life and even human security depend on his interaction with nature. This interaction should be reasonable.

3. Nature exists in the form of systems of various levels, all elements of the systems are interconnected. The global ecosystem is the biosphere. Man has a special role in the transformation of the biosphere and must take responsibility for its fate.

Understanding the importance of environmental issues leads to the recognition of the need for environmental education. But, based on the approach to understanding the essence of environmental problems, there is also a different understanding of the essence of environmental education. The first approach is implemented in the practice of religious education and is aimed at admiring and admiring nature, seeing its beauty and forming a desire to preserve divine harmony.

The most common for secular educational organizations is the adoption of the second approach and the conduct of rational and pragmatic education aimed at realizing the exhaustion of nature's resources and the emergence of a desire for rational environmental management; to accept the fact of human destruction of nature, awakening shame for man and recognizing moral duty to nature; to awaken fear of a possible environmental disaster and the formation of environmental responsibility for his behavior. But it is this approach that least affects the spiritual and spiritual aspects of the child's relationship with nature, leads to the emergence of pessimism about the development of mankind, to the acceptance of the idea of the irreversibility of the ecological crisis and the regulation of behavior based on the rule "Oh, it doesn't matter ...".

We believe that only the third approach can be effective today, the pedagogical implementation of which is aimed at discovering one's unity with nature, discovering nature in oneself and feeling oneself a part of nature.

Choosing a meaningful basis for environmental education based on this approach, we relied on the idea of the interconnection of living and inanimate nature, the interpenetration of worlds, the analogy of the micro and macrocosm. The life of each being, being a value in itself, is at the same time part of a more highly organized system: "everything is connected to everything." The ancients perceived the world in its indivisibility through the concept of elements, which provide an eternal cycle of substances and thereby preserve the interconnection of the world with each individual being, combining the elements of water, air, energy and earth. In the history of archaic cultures, including the Slavs, these ideas of the interpenetration of worlds to the deep personal world are seen, when the innermost Self acquires the meaning of existence in time and space. Folk cultural traditions in ceremonial, linguistic, ornamental, and playful forms preserve this knowledge. Russian calendar traditions have found their embodiment in the calendar layout of the content, in an attentive careful attitude to the language, the word in its innermost sense of addressing any living being from a blade of grass to a mother, to the objective world around us.

We have identified some specific requirements for a teacher who is able to conduct environmental education within the framework of our approach:

- knowledge of the basics of ecological culture with priority to the qualitative characteristics of life, spirituality, reason; personal acceptance of the ecological imperative;
- empathic attitude to nature, to people;
- the ability to provide the child with the opportunity to see the problem for himself and the way to solve it;

- the ability to solve problems of teaching and upbringing not only in the classroom, but also in other forms of interaction, including in creating situations where children commit acts, knowledge of contextual pedagogy;
- attention to small things and their correlation with global phenomena of the world;
- demonstration of trust in the child, his feelings and feelings;
- mastery of techniques of self-exploration, relaxation and control of emotions, the ability to help children master these techniques.

The main goal of ecological education in the preschool period is the formation of the emotional basis of ecological culture: the child's empathic attitude to the surrounding nature, the feeling of oneself as a part of nature, involved in interaction with it and obeying uniform laws. Such an attitude is a necessary condition for developing ecological behavior in the world around us, which is expressed in the form of a lively interest in nature, humanistic and aesthetic experiences, a practical willingness to take care and create beauty around oneself; carefully handle things not only because it is someone's work, but also because the materials spent, taken from nature.

The educational space is voluminous, it absorbs the influence of the family, educational institutions, cultural and additional education institutions, and the media, being a factor of multilevel and diverse impact. A large place in many families is now occupied by television. A lively, bright, dynamic screen attracts the child's gaze. But, unfortunately, children's programs, especially for preschool children, do not always have a positive educational character, the content of many of them does not meet the elementary requirements of moral culture and the cognitive needs of children. Nevertheless, the cognitive and aesthetic value of children's programs is very high, and, as practice shows, not only for children, but also for their parents. According to psychologists, the mass media today have a greater impact on children than educational institutions.

Since the idea of creating a children's environmental program arose, a problem arose: who will be a guide for children on a journey through the mysterious, magical, alluring world of nature; who will help young viewers immerse themselves in it, feel like not just contemplators, but creators of this world, without becoming a dry and tedious moralizer? The children had to accept this guide, trust him, and see him as a friend and helper. In our opinion, it should have been a toy, some kind of character, not yet familiar to children, but at the same time causing a desire to get to know and get to know him better, to want to hear what he says, see what he shows, listen to his advice. First of all, he had to be a bearer of ecological culture, something that we would like to endow with the souls, hearts and minds of our viewers. There were many opinions about the name of the main character of the environmental program. They were expressed by children, parents, teachers of our team, and employees of the broadcasting company, but everyone agreed that his name should contain the whole meaning of this program, and it should be easy to pronounce, be bright, warm, gentle, sonorous. Thus was born a fairy-tale character endowed with human qualities, to whom we gave the name "Fontanelle". The word spring is the same root as the words Homeland, genus, kin and comes from the name of the Slavic god of the Genus, according to the thoughts of our Slavic ancestors, the creator of the Universe, Earth and man. Springs feed the beginning of large and small rivers, they are inexhaustible, clean, in constant motion and renewal. We would really like the Rodnichok program to have all these qualities. In each program, some problem of the children's immediate

environment is brought up for discussion: a broken tree in the yard, a hungry tit outside the window, a sick hamster, garbage on lawns, etc., and "Fontanelle" helps to solve these problems, which, along with the children-viewers, is gaining knowledge, skills and experience of communicating with nature. They grow up together, get smarter, grow up.

A special feature of our program is the participation of children from our kindergarten in it. Seeing their peers on the screen, young viewers watch the program with more interest, this encourages them to engage in activities, striving to do something just like the children on the screen. Different types of activities are included in each program: This includes observing plants and animals, games, targeted walks, excursions, conversations, meetings with literary characters, educational games, performing creative tasks, etc. We strive to show maximum ingenuity, creativity, artistry in order to really give children the opportunity to "get infected" with our emotions, involve them in joint action and in all cases of experiencing joy and satisfaction from the good deeds done.

When our preschool institution started its activities in the direction of environmental education and upbringing, we faced the tasks of proper organization and greening of the developing subject environment. The creation of such an environment, its maintenance at the right level, improvement and subsequent use in teaching activities is an important condition for environmental education of preschoolers. With the help of sponsors, we made our dream come true, within a few months we created a wonderful phytobar room, where children are offered a set of vitamin teas and herbal infusions after classes in the pool. The health-improving value of phytobar is complemented by cognitive and aesthetic. During the tea party, children have conversations about the features of medicinal plants, their places of growth, their beauty and attractiveness.

The developing potential of the territory near the garden is expanding: ecological minisystems have been created, the living natural environment is being enriched, game walking modules are being expanded, etc.

We conducted a diagnostic study aimed at studying the attitude of parents to environmental education, their ideas about the tasks and problems of modern education. 73 people took part in the anonymous survey. To the question of whether you consider environmental education relevant, 86% of the affirmative answers were received. A small part of parents (11%) give its interpretation related to the need to think about the future, change this future, as well as with an understanding of its moral and general development essence.

We see the result of our work in children, in the moral education of our graduates, which is noted by school teachers, in the support of the work carried out by the teaching staff of the Preschool educational institution by parents who act as our allies in the environmental education of children.

References:

1. Akimova T.A., Haskin V.V. Fundamentals of eco-development: textbook. the manual. - M.: Publishing House of the Russian Academy of Economics, 1994. - 312 p.
2. Lopatina A.A., Skrebtsova M.V. Tales of Mother Earth. Environmental education through fairy tales, poems and creative tasks. - 2nd ed. - Moscow: Amrita-Rus, 2008. - 256 p.
3. Nikolaeva S.N. Theory and methodology of ecological education of children: studies. a student's manual. higher education. institution. - M.: Academy, 2002. - 336 p.

4. Abdullina L.B., Petrova T.I., Berzina R.F. The use of the game in the environmental education of preschoolers. The world of science, culture, and education. 2017; 5 (66): 5 - 7.
5. Serebryakova T.A. Environmental education in preschool age. Moscow: Akademiya, 2008.
6. Petrova T.I., Valieva Ya.S. 'Ekologo-pedagogicheskaya rabota s doshkol'nikami. Materialy VII Mezhdunarodnoj zaочноj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii, 12 oktyabrya 2017 g. Sterlitamak: SF BashGU, 2017: 232 - 235.
7. Abdullina L.B., Petrova T.I., Berzina R.F. Osobennosti organizacii 'ekologicheskogo vospitaniya doshkol'nikov. Mir nauki, kul'tury, obrazovaniya. 2017; 4 (65): 5 - 6.
8. Petrova T.I. Teoriya i tehnologii 'ekologicheskogo obrazovaniya detej. Sterlitamak: SF BashGU, 2013.
9. Abdullina L.B., Petrova T.I., Berzina R.F. Ispol'zovanie igry v 'ekologicheskom obrazovanii doshkol'nikov. Mir nauki, kul'tury, obrazovaniya. 2017; 5 (66): 5 - 7.
10. Serebryakova T.A. 'Ekologicheskoe obrazovanie v doshkol'nom vozraste. Moskva: Akademiya, 2008.

